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BIOACTIVITY PROFILING OF BERMET WINES: *IN VITRO* HYPOGLYCEMIC POTENTIAL

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Bermet is a specially flavored wine, which is made from grapes from vineyards on the slopes of Fruška Gora (Vojvodina, Serbia) with the addition of up to 26 different aromatic medicinal plants. This wine has been produced since the 15th century according to the traditional procedure, but until now data on chemical composition and biological activities of these wines are scarce. The aim of this study was to evaluate *in vitro* effect of 7 red and 5 white Bermet wine on α -amylase and α -glucosidase, digestive enzymes involved in carbohydrate metabolism. It is well known that polyphenols have certain biological activity and therefore can contribute to the health benefits of medicinal plants and wine. Therefore, quantitative analysis of 7 phenolic acids, 6 flavonoids, 2 stilbens, 15 anthocyanine glucosides, galactosides and arabinosides by HPLC-UV/VIS technique was applied to elucidate differences in samples phenolic profile. Also, the content of total phenols, tanins, flavonoids and monomeric anthocyanins were evaluated by spectrophotometric methods. Analysed Bermet wines had moderate hypoglycemic potential: activity ranged from 100 to 936 μ g acarbose eq/mL of wine (α -amylase) and 1.79 to 46.6 mg acarbose eq/mL of wine (α -glucosidase). The most abundant polyphenol compounds in examined samples were gallic acid (2.3–51.3 mg/L) and catechin (to 19.5 mg/L). Stilben piceid was detected in some samples in higher content (0.3–9.9 mg/L) than resveratol (0.1–9.9 mg/L). Unexpectedly, anthocyanins were detected in only four samples. Presented results are just a part of intensive research on biochemical and health-safety aspect of the quality of Bermet wine. Overall results should elucidate possibility of health benefits of moderate consumption of Bermet wines, but also to contribute, at least partially, to the increase of recognition of Serbian Bermet wines on domestic and world market.

Keywords: Bermet wine, polyphenols, α -amylase, α -glucosidase

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